

Imam Abu Hanifa And His Educational Thought

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Abstract

God has honored man and bestowed upon him countless bounties, and surrounded him with bounties that do not expire. The Almighty said: (And We have certainly honored the children of Adam and carried them on the land and sea and provided for them of the good things and preferred them over much of what We have created, with [definite] preference), he increased his dignity by breathing into him from his spirit and endowing him with sane, thinking humanity and the advantage with which he distinguished him from all other creatures, and man cannot carry out the tasks of the caliphate in isolation from the revelation that shows him the method and the basis on which he builds his perceptions of the universe and life.

Islamic education seeks permanently to reconcile the goals of life with the necessities of society and human inclinations, and its ultimate goal is to find balance in the soul of the individual, which in turn achieves balance in society in a comprehensive manner, and the commandments in Islamic education are among the important pillars on which the educational process is built, it is one of the successful methods of raising a person, as these commandments contributed to building the Islamic personality that was distinguished by the clarity of its features and its uniqueness from others in its behavior, where his commandments included an ample stock of legal texts until they were comprehensive.

Therefore, this study came to deal with the educational ideas and concepts of Imam Abu Hanifa, so the first chapter included the problem of the study, its importance, objectives, questions and methodology. As for the second chapter, it dealt with a brief narration of the Imam's biography, his life, his doctrine, his elders, and his scholarly works until his death.

The third chapter came to complete "the subject of the study, which is the educational thought of Imam Abu Hanifa, to be in five main axes:

First: the social dimension.

Second: Calling for knowledge and linking knowledge to action.

Third: behavioral education.

Fourth: Spiritual education.

Fifth: Fiqh al-Maqasid

This study presents the correct and bright image of Imam Abu Hanifa and his educational thought and the virtues that emerged from his commandments in education that refine the human soul and keep it away from vices.

Introduction

Imam Abu Hanifa (699-767 AD) is a seminal figure in Islamic jurisprudence, renowned for founding the Hanafi school of thought, the most widely followed amongst the Sunni Muslims globally. Born in Kufa, Iraq, Abu Hanifa's ideas and methodologies greatly influenced the development of Islamic law (Sharia) and its application across diverse contexts. However, his contributions were not confined solely to legal theory; Imam Abu Hanifa's educational philosophies, often underemphasized, have had an enduring impact on the pedagogical approaches within Islamic education.

Imam Abu Hanifa advocated for an interactive and dynamic approach to learning, encouraging inquiry and intellectual engagement. His teaching methodology was unique, characterized by active student participation, questioning, and group discussions. He fostered a learning environment that emphasized the application of knowledge, reasoning, and ethical conduct.

Furthermore, Imam Abu Hanifa's educational thought stressed the importance of adapting teaching methods to cater to individual differences among learners. He believed in the significance of moral education and character development, viewing these as integral aspects of holistic education.

Despite the importance of Imam Abu Hanifa's contributions to Islamic education, there is a noticeable scarcity of comprehensive research in this area. This paper aims to fill this gap by examining Imam Abu Hanifa's educational thought in detail and discussing its implications for contemporary Islamic education.

The study Problem

The main problem of this study lies in the absence of an important aspect of the legacy of Imam Abu Hanifa, represented by his educational commandments.

Previous studies that dealt with educational ideas and concepts were limited to studying and highlighting the jurisprudential aspect of Imam Abu Hanifa, without referring to his educational commandments, which are considered among the treasures of the Islamic heritage rich in educational values, and in all fields, educational education, moral education, behavioral education, political education, and spiritual education.

The Study Importance

The commandments of Imam Abu Hanifa had a great impact on preserving and preserving the identity of the nation from the delusions of the era that witnessed an openness to new civilizations following the expansion of Islamic conquests, and also helped advance scientific research according to disciplined rules, and his commandments were distinguished by their close connection with the Holy Quran, and the Sunnah of the Prophet and what it contained of educational ideas, concepts and values, as his commandments had a great impact in modifying and correcting behavior.

Objectives of the study

The study aims to the following:

1. Getting to know Imam Abi Hanifa, through a brief translation of his life and scientific upbringing.
2. A statement of the educational concepts included in the commandments of Imam Abu Hanifa.
3. Demonstrating the extent to which the educational concepts included in these commandments relate to the foundations of Islamic education.

The Study Questions

The study seeks to answer the following question:

What are the educational aspects included in the commandments of Imam Abu Hanifa?

Study Approach

In his study, the researcher adopted the analytical historical method according to the following steps:

1. Refer to historical and documentary sources in translating the lives of imams, such as: Al-Dhahabi's Biographies of the Flags of the Nobles, Al-Tabari's History, and other modern sources and references.
2. Books related to the topic.
3. Islamic education books

Chapter Two

Imam Abu Hanifa Al-Numan: Biography and his life

His name and lineage

He is the imam, the jurist of the religion, the scholar of Iraq, Abu Hanifah al-Nu`man ibn Thabit ibn Zuti al-Kufi, the mawla of Banu Taymullah ibn Tha'labah, and Zuti, his grandfather, was from the people of Kabul, He was owned, so he was set free. However, this narration, which says that Abu Hanifa's grandfather was a slave, is opposed by another narration that denies slavery on the authority of Abu Hanifa's grandfather, which was narrated by his grandson Ismail, who says: (I am Ismail Ibn Hammad Ibn al-Nu`man Ibn Thabit Ibn al-Marzian from the sons of Faris al-Ahrar, and by God, slavery never occurred to us, my grandfather was born in the year 80, and Thabit went to Ali bin Abi Talib, may God be pleased with him, when he was young.

The Persian origin from which Abu Hanifa descended, and the fact that his grandfather was a slave and then emancipated according to the first narration, all of this does not detract from the fate of Abu Hanifa, and does not harm him in his honor even if slavery took place on him, because a person does not transcend his race, lineage, or freedom, but he exalts his piety, knowledge, and benefit to the nation, and this was the matter of the imam. God Almighty said: (The most honorable of you with God is the most pious of you, and the Messenger, may God's prayers and peace be upon him, confirms it by saying: (There is no superiority for an Arab over a non-Arab except with piety).

His birth and upbringing

Abu Hanifa was born in Kufa in the year eighty of the Hijrah, in the life of the young companions, Abdullah bin Abi Awfa, Sahl bin Saad Al-Saadi, Aba Al-Tufayl Amer bin Wathila and Abdullah bin Al-Harith bin Juz' met with them, and Anas bin Malik saw Kufa when he arrived, and he did not take from them.

Ibn Khalkan reported a narration that the birth of Abu Hanifa was in the year sixty-one of the Hijrah, The researcher believes that this narration is not correct, for the following:

Firstly: That all the sources that translated the life of Abu Hanifa confirm that his death was in the year one hundred and fifty of the Hijra, and that he lived seventy years, so his birth would be in the year eighty of the Hijrah.

Secondly: Ibn Katheer mentioned that Al-Mansur assigned Abu Hanifa to take over the judiciary in the year 146 AH, and according to the second narration, his age at that time would be eighty-five years, and whoever was at this age could not imagine that he would be assigned to assume positions in the state, especially the position of the judiciary, due to its importance and sensitivity, and the supplies of his requirements that the elderly man may have lost due to his advanced age.

Third: The narrators of the biographies affirm that Abu Hanifa saw Malik bin Anas, may God be pleased with him, and did not take from him, and this cannot be imagined, unless there is something to prevent him, and he is young in the age of Abu Hanifa, since Abu Hanifa did not seek knowledge at that early stage of his life, and if the second narration is true, he would have seen him when he was over thirty years old, and Abu Hanifa at this age had come a long way in seeking knowledge, and with this, the first narration must be preferred over the second narration, the researcher believes that the reason for this is the death of the companions whom he met while he was at an age in which he did not seek knowledge yet. Abdullah bin Abi Awfa died in the year (86) AH in Kufa, Abu Hanifa was still six years old, and Sahel bin Saad Al-Saadi died in the year (88) in Medina, and Omar bin Wathilah (Abu Tufail) died in the year (110) AH in Makkah, the age of Abu Hanifa was thirty years, and it seems that not seeing him and meeting him is the reason for not taking from him, and Abdullah bin Al-Harith bin Juz died in the year (86) AH in Egypt, and Anas bin Malik died in the year (93 AH), Abu Hanifa was still young and did not work with science at the age of thirteen.

As for his upbringing, Abu Hanifa grew up in Kufa and was raised in it and lived most of his life there. His family was a Muslim family of wealth and wealth, and his grandfather went to Ali bin Abi Talib, may God be pleased with him, and gave him the model. Then Ali, may God be pleased with him, prayed for him and his offspring to be blessed.

His work

Abu Hanifa was engaged in trade, and he had a store where he sold vegetables, and he was bringing goods to Baghdad, And this is what he narrated from himself, he said: (I passed by Al-Sha'bi while he was sitting, and he called me, and he said to me: To whom do you differ? then he said to me: Do not be negligent, and you should look into knowledge and sit with scholars, for I see in you vigilance and movement.

Despite Abu Hanifa's orientation to knowledge, he did not stop his trade, and this was mentioned by Al-Muwaffaq Al-Makki in the narration of Yusuf bin Khalid Al-Samti describing the daily life of Abu Hanifa, and he said: (Saturday was for his needs, he did not attend the council, and he does not attend the market, he devotes his time to the affairs of his house and his estate, and he used to sit in the market from the forenoon until the first, and on Fridays he had a lawsuit gathering his friends in his house, and he cooked for them all kinds of food, and he had a partner who worked with him in his business, this helped him to combine trade and knowledge seeking.

The request for knowledge

Abu Hanifa grew up in Kufa, which witnessed an active scientific movement, and his era was distinguished by the multiplicity of types of sciences, so that each science became its imams and its notables, so the science of hadith, jurisprudence and readings emerged, along with other sciences such as theology, which spread in that period, due to the multiplicity of teams and boredoms, it was natural for Abu Hanifa to accept knowledge and receive from his imams, and Al-Shaabi encouraged him to seek knowledge because he saw in it the signs of intelligence, so he accepted the request for knowledge, and directed his aspiration towards it, so he became a proverb in his time.

And the diversity of sciences in his era had a great impact on the diversity of his culture, and he gained a lot of luck from every science, so he memorized the Qur'an on Asim bin Abi Al-Nujoud, one of the seven reciters, and he learned it with Hammad bin Abi Suleiman, he took the hadeeth from Abu Shihab al-Zuhri

The first thing he learned was the science of theology and he reached a high position in it, so he used to debate with the people of the sects and the people of the denominations such as the Kharijites and the Mu'tazila, then he turned away from him and turned to jurisprudence. Then a woman came to me and said: A man has a wife, a slave girl who wanted him to divorce her for the Sunnah. How often should he divorce her? I did not know what to say, so I ordered her to ask Hamada and then come back and tell me, I asked Hamada, and he said: He divorces her while she is pure from menstruation and sexual intercourse, then he leaves her until she has menstruated two times, and if she does ghusl, then she is permissible for the husbands, she came back and told me, so I said: I do not need to speak, and I took my shoes and sat with Hammad, so I used to hear a question, so I memorized his saying, then he repeats it from tomorrow, so I memorize it and his companions make mistakes, so he said: No one sits in the chest of the ring with my shoes except for Abu Hanifa, so I accompanied him for ten years, then my soul challenged me to seek leadership, so I wanted to retire from him and sit in a circle for myself, so I went out one day in the evening, and my intention was to do so, I came and sat

with him, and that night came the news of a relative of his who died in Basra and left money and he had no heir other than him, so he ordered me to sit in his place. It was nothing but that he went out until I received questions that I did not hear from him, so I was answering and writing my answer, so he was absent for two months, then he came, so I presented the issues to him, and they were about sixty questions, so he agreed with me on forty and disagreed with me on twenty, so I vowed to myself that I would not leave him until he died, so I did not leave him until he died.

And Abu Hanifa was eager to seek knowledge and was passionate about it, insisting on asking his sheikh until his teacher's chest became narrow because of his many questions. Abu Hanifa said: I bound Hamada in a way that I do not know that anyone bound anyone as I bound him, and I used to ask the most, so he might get tired of me and say: O Abu Hanifa, my side is swollen and my chest is tight. and Abu Hanifa was distinguished by his memorization and the strength of his memory. On the authority of Abdullah bin Amr, he said: I was in the Al-Amash council, and a man came to him and asked him about an issue, and he did not answer him about it. He said: From such-and-such hadith you told him. He said: Al-A'mash said: We are the pharmacists and you are the doctors, in this narration, there is an indication of the status of Abu Hanifa among the scholars and their confidence in his knowledge.

His qualities

Abu Hanifa was on a large side of good morals, and he enjoyed a great deal of its virtues, and qualities gathered in him that were dispersed in others. Al-Muafi bin Imran Al-Mawsili said: (Abu Hanifa, may God have mercy on him, had ten qualities. There was never one of them except that he became the leader of his people and dominated his tribe, piety, honesty, generosity, jurisprudence, politeness to people, sincere chivalry, devotion to what is beneficial, lengthy silence, correctness in speech, and the aid of eagerness is an enemy, whether a friend or a friend

Al-Fudayl bin Ayyad said: Abu Hanifa was a man of jurisprudence, known for his jurisprudence, famous for his piety, ample wealth, known for his virtues over those who circumambulate him, patient in teaching knowledge day and night, good night, a lot of silence, little talk until his question is answered in forbidden and lawful, and he was good at pointing to the truth, fleeing from the money of the Sultan.

Among his qualities are trustworthiness and piety, and these two qualities are inseparable and do not appear except when he is able to contradict them. A person cannot claim trust unless he is exposed to the temptation of money, nor piety until his hand reaches the suspicions between what is permissible and what is forbidden, so he stops his hand from it.

Abu Hanifa rose in the ladder of piety and the runways of fear and fear of God Almighty until he reached the goal, and piety was represented in him in all its forms and forms, and it covered all aspects of his life, he was pious in his fatwa, and pious in his earnings, far from everything that wrongs his religion or defames his chivalry, and his biography testified to that and was confirmed by the scholars of his time and those who came after them.

In addition to that, Abu Hanifa was a generous, generous horse, spending a lot, and this was confirmed by the biographers, and his generosity reached that he was not cutting off his dues, even if it cost him a lot of money, he says: What if I saw Hamada? He said: Abu Hanifa used to support me and my children for ten years, and I have not seen anyone who possesses more praiseworthy qualities than he.

Despite the wealth of Abu Hanifa, the abundance of his money, and the desire of the world for him, he was an example of asceticism in it, the desire for it, and the turning away from collecting its debris, he was struck with whips, and it was said to him: Take the debt, so he was patient through good times and bad times, and he did not enter into what others used to seek and wish for.

His Doctrine

Abu Hanifa built his jurisprudential school of thought on seven fundamentals, four of which are agreed upon by the jurists, which are the Qur'an, Sunnah, consensus, and analogy, and three are disputed over them, which are: the Companion's saying, approval, and custom. These principles are explained by the saying of Abu Hanifa himself, where he says: (I take the Book of God, and if I do not find it, then the Sunnah of the Messenger of God, may God's prayers and peace be upon him, and if I do not find it, then I take the sayings of the Companions, I take the sayings of whoever I want from them, and I do not deviate from their sayings to the sayings of others, (I take the Book of God, and if I do not find it, then the Sunnah of the Messenger of God, may God's prayers and peace be upon him, and if I do not find it, then I take the sayings of the Companions, I take the sayings of whoever I want from them, and I do not deviate from their sayings to the sayings of others.

The matter of Abu Hanifa in dealing with the fundamentals on which his doctrine is based is like that of the great scholars in giving precedence to the text over opinion and analogy, if you have authentic hadiths from the Messenger of God, may God's prayers and peace be upon him, then say it and leave what I say, for I say it even if you do not hear from me, and he said: (If the hadith on the authority of the Messenger of God, may God's prayers and peace be upon him, is authentic, and I said something, then I will retract my statement and say that).

In addition to the abundant knowledge of Abu Hanifa, with which he gained a distinguished position among the scholars of his time, and with his superior ability to ijtihad, deduction, and accuracy of understanding until his doctrine became one of the four doctrines that Muslims received with acceptance, he does not become fanatical to his opinion, but rather acquiesces to the truth if it appears at the hands of others. This was explained by his saying (This is our opinion, and it is the best of what we are able to do, so whoever comes to us with a better one than our saying is more right than us) that this saying indicates the extent of his sincerity in seeking the truth and his preference over the desires of the soul and its impulses from the love of fame and the desire for status and status among people, and this sincerity is what brought him to the height of his position, because it is a fruit of piety in which God Almighty said: (And fear God, and God will teach you).

His elders

Abu Hanifa approached the quest for knowledge with all zeal and sincerity of intention, and was educated in most of the cultures that were in his era, then he went after that and studied the Qur'an and took jurisprudence and hadith, so he took all the knowledge from his imams until he excelled and established his jurisprudential school of thought, which his students carried after him and worked to spread it.

The diversity of Abu Hanifa's culture indicates that he took his knowledge from a large number of scholars who were his contemporaries, and what helped him in that was his scientific trips and frequenting to the Sacred House of God and meeting the scholars of Makkah such as Atta bin Abi Rabah, who is considered the greatest and best sheikh for him, according to what Abu Hanifa stated to him, likewise, his commercial trips had an impact on his many elders.

Abu Hanifa was a student at the hands of Asim bin Abi Al-Nujoud, so he took the Qur'an from him, and jurisprudence from his sheikh Hammad, who adhered to him for eighteen years, and the hadith on the authority of Ibn Shihab Al-Zuhri, and it was narrated on the authority of Malik bin Anas, who is younger than him, and also on the authority of Shayban the grammarian.

Scientific implications

The scientific works left by Abu Hanifa, which influenced Islamic jurisprudence, and worked to expand perceptions and understanding, indicate a distinguished personality among the scholars of the Islamic nation, and this distinction earned it that status, until it became a science referred to as Lebanon. His scientific works are represented by his writings, his students, and his jurisprudential school of thought, which we touched on previously, so I will confine myself here to explaining his writings and students.

First: his books

Due to the diversity of cultures and the emergence of teams in the era of Abu Hanifa, people's need for codes and literature in jurisprudence, hadith and beliefs emerged, so he had a lot of luck from these literature, which are:

- 1 -The Book of Response to Fatalism
- 2 -The book of the scholar and the learner
- 3 -His letter to Al-Basti
- 4 -Knowledge by land and sea, east and west, far and near
- 5 -The Greater Jurisprudence Book
- 6 -His letter to Othman Al-Batti, the judge of Basra
- 7 -The Book of Assignments
- 8- Book of Conditions.

In the hadith, he has fifteen Musnads, which were collected in a book called Jami` al-Musanid, arranged on the chapters of jurisprudence.

Second: his students

It was narrated on the authority of Abu Hanifa a lot of creation, as it was a kiss for the students of knowledge, and among the most famous of them: Zakhar bin Al-Hudhayl, Al-Qadi Abu Yusuf, Muhammad bin Al-Hassan, Asad bin Amr, Al-Hassan bin Ziyad Al-Lulu'i, Noah Al-Jame', Waki', Abu Naim, Abd Al-Razzaq, Hamza Al-Zayyat, Hashim, Abdullah bin Al-Mubarak.

His Death

Abu Hanifa died in the year one hundred and fifty AH, the cause of his death differed, but the most likely narration confirms that he died after consuming a poisoned drink, Al-Khatib Al-Baghdadi narrated on the authority of Zakhar bin Al-Hudhayl, he said: Abu Hanifa used to speak out loud in the days of Ibrahim, so I said to him:By God, you are not with him until the ropes are placed around our necks. Soon, a letter from Al-Mansur came to Isa bin Musa to carry Abu Hanifa.He carried it to Baghdad and lived for fifteen days, then gave it to drink and died, in the year one hundred and fifty AH.

Chapter Three

The educational axes of Imam Abu Hanifa

Imam Abu Hanifa set himself up to advise and guide the nation, and direct it towards virtue, goodness, and excellency matters, and advised and warned it of the consequence of deviating from the teachings of Islam through the commandments that he presented to all people, and to his students in particular, and since members of society are affected by the course of events, they also influence them, through their dealings with them, and by harnessing matters to confront them, and they may have had a share in shaping the event according to their status, and through their different positions. This is what Imam Abu Hanifa called for in his book *The Learner and the Learner*. Which he directed to Abu Muqatil, where he said: The scholar cannot close his eyes to what is happening around him, on the pretext that what does not fall under his hearing and sight, he is not responsible for it.

Imam Abu Hanifa left a great impact and a prominent role in various fields, whether in the field of science and education, in the field of politics, or in the field of social life, as the researcher put it in several axes:

First: the social dimension

Social life has been affected by the commandments of Imam Abu Hanifa, and this was evident through the emergence of new ideas and contents, which were included in his commandments, one of his commandments that he recommended and directed to his students was to warn them against mixing with the sultans and caliphs, and he refused their gifts, so there was a great distance between him and the caliphs, so he would not enter upon the caliph unless he invited him and asked him to do so, and he rejected the caliphs' desire to assume positions in the state, and this is part of what he spoke to Yusuf bin Yaqoub, where the imam said: (O Yaqoub... the Sultan's approval and great status if he took the pledge of allegiance with its right, and beware of lying in his hands, and do not enter upon him at all times and in every case, unless he invites you for a scholarly need, because if you multiply the difference to him, he will belittle and underestimate you..., and if he offers you something of his deeds, do not accept it except after you know that he pleases you and pleases your religion, your Messenger, and your doctrine, so that he does not need to commit the doctrine of others in government. Abu Hanifa realized the seriousness of the relationship between rulers and scholars, whether positive or negative, and Abu Hanifa himself was martyred as a result of his principles that refined the relationship between rulers and scholars, as it was reported in some sources of history that Al-Mansur Al-Abbasi put poison in his food.

Abu Hanifa linked religious virtues to daily life, and applied that to himself, his companions, his students, and all those who mixed with him.

With regard to marriage, Imam Abu Hanifa recommended not to get married except after one becomes familiar with the competence in himself, both financially and physically, and by delaying it for those who want to work in seeking knowledge, because of the consequences and costs that entail, so he said in his will to his student Abu Yusuf: (And do not get married until you know that you are able to fulfill all her needs, and seek knowledge first, then collect money from lawful things, then work with marriage, because if you work with asking for money at the time of learning, you will be unable to seek knowledge).

Likewise, Imam Abu Hanifa believes that a man may marry a virgin woman, and that she does not have a father or a mother. Abu Hanifa said: (And do not marry a woman who has a husband, father, mother, son, or daughter if she is able, except on the condition that no one else from among her relatives enters upon her, because if a woman has money, her father claims that all her money belongs to him... And he said: (Beware of marrying one with sons and daughters).

Imam Abu Hanifa also recommended marriage that the man be able to bear its costs and consequences, and after the man finds in himself the competence to perform the rights incurred by him towards his family, he intends to marry.

In order to maintain the stability and continuity of marital life, Islam enjoins the husband to treat the wife well, to treat her kindly, and to awaken in himself a sense of responsibility towards her. The imam recommended not to speak about other women in her hands. And that is due to the intense jealousy that settles itself. The Messenger of God, may God's prayers and peace be upon him, said: "Be kind to women, for women were created from a rib, and the crooked part of the rib is its upper part.

Also, one of the most important commandments of Imam Abu Hanifa is to take care of the rights of parents, so it is obligatory to be kind to them and accompany them with kindness and kindness and not to offend them, or to dislike them, even if they are unbelievers, because they have the right to fatherhood over their son. And Islam forbids showing pity for them, God Almighty said: (Either one or both of them reach old age with you, do not say to them a "f" and do not rebuke them, but speak to them a kind word.

Likewise, there are a number of important social matters recommended by Imam Abu Hanifa, including the right of the neighbor, as he said: (And what you saw on your neighbor, then cover him up, for it is a trust with you, and people's secrets are not revealed, acting according to the rights ensuing between neighbors establishes the relations of affection and love among them, and consolidates the foundations of compassion and cooperation. Abu Yusuf said (Abu Hanifa had a neighbor and he used to drink in the tavern, then he would return at night singing and saying:

They lost me and any boy they lost For a foul day and a severe gap

So he came back one night, and Al-Taif took him and imprisoned him, so Abu Hanifa lost his voice, so he asked about him, and he was told: Al-Taif was imprisoned, so Abu Hanifa spoke about him until he was released, he said to him: Boy, did you see us losing you?

Islam gave the neighbor with kinship rights that surpassed other neighbors, because of kinship, and because he is one of the kinsmen whom the Holy Qur'an recommended, the Almighty said: (And fear Allah, whom you ask for, and the wombs. Indeed, Allah has been a watcher over you).

Second: the call to knowledge and linking knowledge and work

Science was a matter of great care for Imam Abu Hanifa, as he is the scholar and the learner, and he made science the way to reform humanity and its happiness, and that it is more important than working to earn sustenance, in the sense that one starts studying first and is satisfied with the little that helps him in his affairs, as knowledge is worthy of providing one with the means for a good life, and he says in his will: (If you remain ten years without earning or sustenance, do not turn away from knowledge, if you turn away from him, then your life will be miserable according to what the Almighty said: (And whoever turns away from my remembrance, he will have a miserable life).

Knowledge is dhikr, and dhikr is worship. All texts acknowledge that gatherings of knowledge are gatherings of worship, and Abu Hanifa gives priority to seeking knowledge over marriage. Seeking money in preparation for marriage prevents a person from seeking knowledge. Therefore, seeking knowledge is more deserving of precedence, as he says in his will: (And do not get married until you know that you are able to fulfill all her needs, i.e. the needs of the wife, and seek knowledge first, then collect money from what is lawful, then get married, because if you are preoccupied with asking for money at the time of learning, you will be unable to seek knowledge).

And Imam Abu Hanifa explains the way to deal with scholars, and his need if a person is a foreigner to them in their country, and he says: (And if you enter a town that has people of knowledge, do not take it for yourself, but rather be one of its people so that they know that you do not intend their prestige, otherwise they will revolt against you as a whole and challenge your doctrines).

Abu Hanifa also recommends the scholars to mention their teachers who have moved to God's mercy and ask forgiveness for them, and Abu Hanifa used to ask forgiveness for his teacher Hammad with his parents after every prayer, as he says: (And remember death, and ask forgiveness for your teachers and those from whom you took knowledge, and persevere in reciting the Qur'an, and increase the number of graves, sheikhs, and blessed places).

Abu Hanifa linked knowledge to work, so the stage of knowledge is a stage prior to action, so it is not possible for a person to do something that he is ignorant of, because the result will not be as required. Abu Hanifa said to his student: (Know that action follows knowledge, just as the limbs follow sight, so knowledge is accompanied by easy action. It is more beneficial than ignorance with a lot of action, and similar to that, the little provision that is necessary in the competition along with being guided by it, is more beneficial than ignorance than the abundant provision).

Seeking knowledge requires perseverance, patience, and humility, and it is not attained by haste, and it is necessary for every Muslim, and it is considered one of the duties of the eye, especially knowledge of how to perform acts of worship, as Abu Hanifa said: Understand the religion of God, and leave people and what they have done for themselves, so they need you.

And he said in his will to Ibrahim bin Adham: (O Ibrahim, you have been provided with a good thing from worship, so let knowledge be in your mind, for it is the head of worship and it is the foundation of matters).

Third: behavioral education

The goal of Islamic education is to refine morals and maintain them from every matter that takes them outside the circle of virtue, which is followed by modifying behavior, protecting it from all factors of deviation, and directing it towards goodness, The Almighty said: (But God endeared to you faith and adornment in your hearts, and He hated to you disbelief, transgression, and disobedience).

Virtuous morals and proper behavior based on Islamic foundations and standards are an integral part of the entity of the Muslim community, and they are what distinguishes it from other societies, the Prophet, may God's prayers and peace be upon him, said: "The most perfect of believers in faith are those who are best in character."

Islamic education has performed miracles. It worked on shaping the human being in a new way in all aspects of his life, reorganizing his ideas and beliefs, and correcting his view of the Creator, the universe and life. The Holy Qur'an clarified the behavior and ethics of the members of the Muslim community by saying: Successful indeed are the believers (1) those who are humble in their prayers (2) and those who turn away from idle talk (3) and those who are active in zakat (4) And those who guard their private parts (5) except for their wives or what their right hands possess, for they are not to blame. (6) So who seek beyond that, for those are the transgressors (7) and those who are faithful to their trusts and their covenant (8) and those who are observant of their prayers (9)}

Imam Abu Hanifa recommended that the tongue must be preserved and monitored, due to its danger if it is launched without controls and restrictions, as a person is in dire need of wisdom, and it only comes from the effect of silence on the curiosity of speech, and among the signs of faith is leaving speech that is not good, and there are effects that result from not maintaining the tongue, which is backbiting and gossip. On the authority of Abdullah bin Al-Mubarak, he said: I said to Sufyan Al-Thawri: O Abu Abdullah, what kept Abu Hanifa from backbiting! I have never heard him backbiting an enemy of his. He said: By God, he is wiser than letting his good deeds take away from him.

And Yazid bin Harun said: I wrote about a thousand sheikhs, I carried knowledge from them, and I did not see among them more pious than Abu Hanifa .

In addition to that, there are many things that Islam calls for avoiding and rejecting, which is indulging in lusts and pleasures, because they bring misery and unhappiness to the owner, and this is what Imam Abu Hanifa recommended. He also called for avoiding too much laughter because it deadens the heart, reducing women's conversation and babysitting and avoiding miserliness, greed and lying.

Fourth: spiritual education

Spiritual education is considered the first rule on which the educational structure of the Muslim individual is based, and it is the indispensable foundation, the basis of spiritual education is piety, as it occupied the forefront in all religions. The Almighty said:(And He made them obligated to the word of piety, and they were deserving of it and worthy of it).

And piety is the solid foundation on which the building of society is based, and it is the measure of nearness and distance from God Almighty, and we find in the commandments of Imam Abu Hanifa urging piety where he said: And hold fast to piety.

Piety has important effects in regulating the lives of individuals and preserving them from corruption and preserving them from tampering.

Worshiping God, obeying Him, and submitting to His command also emanates from spiritual education. Given the importance of worship in Islam, it has taken the lead in Islamic legislation. What entrusted you of patience, and what bestowed upon you of blessings, and do not be satisfied for yourself with what pleases the public.

Fifth: Maqasid or discretionary jurisprudence

Abu Hanifa was a pioneer in jurisprudence in authoring issues, as he was distinguished from other jurists in that he put issues that had not occurred yet, but their occurrence is possible, if not in the present, then in the future, this was the approach of Abu Hanifa's thinking about future issues, and he had sufficient experience in life for what would happen in the future.

The issues of Abu Hanifa are many and funny, and they reflect a unique jurisprudential mentality, whether the one he used to compose, such as his question, the one he directed to his leaders when he asked him: What do you say about a man who has been away from his family for years, and his wife thought that her husband died, so she got married, then her first husband returned, what does she say about her dowry? Abu Hanifa whispered to those around him, saying: If he spoke a hadith, he would lie, and if he said in his own opinion, he would make a mistake, or the question that he sent to his student Abu Yusuf in order to discourage him from being alone with a seminar, and its reasons have not yet been completed for him, which is the issue of the dress and the shorts and the extent of the shorts entitlement.

Many of the complex issues people used to turn to Abu Hanifa, and Abu Hanifa was with his knowledge and acumen and his intuition seriously had the satisfactory answer.

Conclusion

This study, which briefly dealt with the translation of the life of Imam Abu Hanifa al-Numan and his educational, spiritual, social, and behavioral commandments, showed an important aspect of the educational effects of Abu Hanifa, as one commandment contains more than one educational significance, which in turn worked to consolidate the spiritual structure in the human soul and protect it from eroding factors.

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